

Feeling, Knowing and Being: Philosophical Foundations of Interdisciplinary Thinking

World Philosophy Day - National Institute of Advanced Studies, Bengaluru

Mathematics and Philosophy

P. Venkata Rayudu

NIAS Consciousness Studies Programme

Knowing is a part of Being. The subjective Knowing *vs.* objective Being contrast is reflected in mathematical thinking as three distinct but related Part-Whole relations:

1. General Concepts *vs.* Particulars
2. Subjective *vs.* Objective Logic
3. Abstract Sets *vs.* Discrete Subcategories

First, what is WHOLE? With a whole as a universe of discourse, we notice that talking about things (e.g. tables and chairs) populating a given universe (Furniture) requires things such as words, statements, languages, concepts, theories, symbols, equations, etc., which are not part of the universe (of Furniture). This state-of-affairs changed for good in mathematics with Functorial Semantics (Lawvere, 1963), which is an abstraction of conceptual content that is invariant across subjective presentations (as in recognizing a concept that is invariant across different words such as water, pani, niru that are used to communicate the concept WATER; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 235-236). Given a category of mathematical particulars, say,

graphs, an abstract general or theory of the given graphs is a subcategory of the category of graphs (Lawvere, 2004, p.19). Thus, within mathematical experience, a theory of a thing is a part—a small part—of the thing that accounts for everything about the thing (Lawvere, 1972, pp. 9-10). For example, a theory of sets is a single-element set because every set can be constructed in terms of the basic shape of single-element set and any two functions between sets can be distinguished using basic-shaped figures. Theories are, nevertheless, subjective since they are calculated with respect to a doctrine (which can be thought of as a mathematical perspective); changing the doctrine changes the way things are theorized (Lawvere, 2013).

Second, what is PART? A part of a whole is both itself and its relationship to the whole (Lawvere, 1994a). For example, given a set, a part i.e. a subset of the given set is not merely another [smaller] set, but is a function specifying how the subset is related to the given set. This realization, due to Grothendieck, led to the objectification of the totality of truth values as a universal mapping property that a universe of discourse may have. If a universe of discourse (e.g. category of sets) has a truth value object, then every part (subset) of any object (set) of the universe can be represented using its truth value object ($\{\text{false}, \text{true}\}$; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 335-357). Equally importantly, the truth value object of a category is determined by the parts of objects constituting the theoretical essence (subcategory of basic shapes) of the given category. In the category of sets, the two truth values (false, true) correspond to the two parts (nothing, everything, respectively) of the single-element set, which is the basic shape of sets. Also note that the knowing of objects of a category in terms of its basic shapes (as noted in the previous section) is dual or opposite to the knowing of objects in terms of its truth value object (of the present section). This duality is essentially the contrast between theoretical essence and logical form or that between geometry of shapes and algebra of logical operations (Lawvere and

Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 11-23; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 369-371). Thus, we arrive at an understanding of logic as the algebra of parts, which, in turn, leads to the objective logic of part-whole analysis of objects to which statements refer to (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 193-212, 239-240). In contrast to the subjective logic of inferring statements from statements based on the form of statements, the objective logic of concepts is sensitive to the content (Lawvere, 1999). For example, given two statements ‘moon is round’ and ‘moon is white’, we conclude ‘moon is round and white’. Notice that drawing this conclusion is based on the form of the statements (subjective presentations), and does not take into account the objective content (meaning) of the words (moon, round, white). The different kinds of cohesion and variation of various categories objectifying different mathematical concepts (e.g. FUNCTION, DYNAMICAL SYSTEM, REFLEXIVE GRAPH) are reflected in their respective objective logics; more specifically, in their degrees of truth, varieties of negation, and admission of logical contradiction, none of which are meaningful in the more familiar subjective logic of mere yes or no answers (Lawvere, 1991, 1994a, 2003; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 212).

Lastly, how does a part of a whole reflect the whole? Mathematical structures of all sorts can be modeled in the category of sets (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 133-151). Abstract sets, by virtue of having no structure, serve as a blank page on which we can print anything (Lawvere, 1994b). Structureless sets are a small part—the only part—of the mathematical universe which reflects all of mathematics. It seemed so until Lawvere axiomatized the Category of Categories (Lawvere, 1966), and pointed out that within any category of structures, there is a part, a structureless subcategory, which is like the category of sets, and hence reflective of all types of structures (Lawvere, 2003, 2004). For example, in the category of dynamical systems, we have

the subcategory of discrete dynamical systems within which any category can be modeled. So, within the category of categories, every part is reflective of the whole!

Summing it all, we—the knowing subjects—are part of the objective reality. The foundational role of reflection—a part of a whole reflecting the whole—calls for an objectification of the concept of REFLECTING as a Category of Reflecting along the lines of the categories of Being *vs.* Becoming (objectified as reflexive graphs *vs.* dynamical systems via the contrasts: space *vs.* time and unity *vs.* change; Lawvere, 1992, 2007). In closing, the seemingly simplistic understanding of ourselves—our place in the vast space of being—as reflective parts, along with its refined reflections sustaining and fuelling mathematical knowing, appears to be resourceful enough to inform the mind-matter problem i.e. guide our thinking about ‘thinking about things and thoughts’.

References

Lawvere, F. W. (1963) Functorial semantics of algebraic theories. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 50, 869-872.

Lawvere, F. W. (1966) The category of categories as a foundation for mathematics. In S. Eilenberg et al. (eds.), *La Jolla Conference on Categorical Algebra*. New York: Springer-Verlag.

Lawvere, F. W. (1972) *Perugia Notes: Theory of Categories over a Base Topos*. Perugia: Universita' di Perugia.

Lawvere, F. W. (1991) Intrinsic co-Heyting boundaries and the Leibniz rule in certain toposes. In A. Carboni, M. C. Pedicchio, and G. Rosolini (eds.), *Category Theory*. New York: Springer-Verlag.

Lawvere, F. W. (1992) Categories of space and of quantity. In J. Echeverria, A. Ibarra and T. Mormann (eds.), *The Space of Mathematics: Philosophical, Epistemological and Historical Explorations*. Berlin: DeGruyter.

Lawvere, F. W. (1994a) Tools for the advancement of objective logic: Closed categories and toposes. In J. Macnamara and G. E. Reyes (eds.), *The Logical Foundations of Cognition*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Lawvere, F. W. (1994b) Cohesive toposes and Cantor's 'lauter Einsen'. *Philosophia Mathematica*, 2, 5-15.

Lawvere, F. W. (1999) Kinship and mathematical categories. In P. Bloom, R. Jackendoff and K. Wynn (eds.), *Language, Logic, and Concepts*. Cambridge: MIT Press.

Lawvere, F. W. (2003) Foundations and applications: Axiomatization and education. *The Bulletin of Symbolic Logic*, 9, 213-224.

Lawvere, F. W. (2004) Functorial semantics of algebraic theories and some algebraic problems in the context of functorial semantics of algebraic theories. Reprints in *Theory and Applications of Categories*, 5, 1-121.

Lawvere, F. W. (2007). Axiomatic cohesion. *Theory and Applications of Categories*, 19, 41-49.

Lawvere, F. W. (2013) Fifty years of functorial semantics. *Celebrating Bill Lawvere and Fifty Years of Functorial Semantics*,
http://www.math.union.edu/~niefiels/13conference/Web/Slides/Fifty_Years_of_Functorial_Semantics.pdf, Accessed 07 May 2015.

Lawvere, F. W. and Rosebrugh, R. (2003) *Sets for Mathematics*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Lawvere, F. W. and Schanuel, S. H. (2009) *Conceptual Mathematics: A First Introduction to Categories*. (2nd ed.) Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.